

POSITION PAPER

Could Pakistan's Current Fuel Price Crisis Mark a Turning Point for the Clean Energy Transition?

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Organisational Profile

Climate Forward Pakistan (CFP) is an independent, youth-led organisation driven by the belief that young people hold the power to drive bold, people-centred climate solutions. What began as a targeted response to gaps in policy, advocacy, and representation has evolved into a comprehensive platform committed to climate justice, equity, and resilience. Grounded in the recognition that youth from climate-vulnerable contexts possess invaluable lived experiences and leadership potential, CFP works actively to bridge the divide between these frontline communities and high-level decision-making spaces.

To ensure youth inclusion moves beyond mere symbolic representation, CFP focuses on policy engagement, capacity building, and community-driven advocacy. Through structured programs, mentorship, and strategic collaboration with civil society, youth networks, and institutional partners, the organisation creates concrete pathways for young people, including children, to understand, access, and meaningfully contribute to the climate agenda. Our continued engagement across national and international platforms shows a strong commitment to ensuring youth participation is informed, prepared, and truly impactful.

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Introduction:

The ongoing Middle East crisis has pushed oil prices to unprecedented levels. Internationally crude oil prices have crossed the \$100 per barrel mark which is expected to further rise as the conflict continues to escalate (Raza & Kiani, 2026). This sudden supply side shock would have many implications for a world that is dependent on fossil fuels for their energy and transportation sector. Pakistan itself is not immune to these surging prices as the government raised 20% in fuel prices making per liter petrol costs PKR 321.17 and diesel PKR 335.86 thus adjusting to global shocks (News Desk, 2026).

Now this price hike would have multiple implications for a country that is already facing energy insecurity, economic instability and inflation. Pakistan dependence on imported fuel is huge as it imports one million barrels of oil from Saudi Arabia and UAE on a monthly basis (Fareedi, 2026). Pakistan's yearly imports of petroleum products span anywhere between \$16 to \$18 billion, which is one third of overall imports. This means that for each \$10 increase in oil prices, there will be a \$2 billion to the country's import bill.

Moreover, missile and drone attacks on oil refineries and shipments have also created uncertainty. Likewise, blockage of the Strait of Hormuz by Iran is hampering overall oil supply to international markets. Recently, higher freight costs due to conflict near shipping lines will make exports more expensive, making the situation critical for Pakistan. However, these geopolitical shocks could be absorbed if adequate energy transition policies are adopted to make renewable energy accessible for power and transport sectors.

Background:

Pakistan's energy mix consists of 27.03% oil, 24.83% coal, 24% gas, 7.54% hydroelectricity, 5% nuclear energy and remaining 12.19% comes from other resources. Pakistan's energy landscape is dominated by thermal power based on imported fuel. This makes the country vulnerable to global price volatility. Moreover, indigenous reserves are depleting at a rapid pace where new discoveries are not able to satisfy domestic energy demand. Apart from costly energy generation, Pakistan has a circular debt of around PKR 2.6 trillion in FY2025 (Ahmad et al., 2025).

This is due to constant under-recoveries, delayed subsidies, and capacity payments issued towards independent power producers (IPPs). Similarly power sector issues such as low recoveries, theft, unreimbursed tariffs and subsidies are adding to the cost of producing energy. In order to resolve the energy crisis, the government is working towards a rapid energy transition which would increase the share of renewable energy in the local grid from 40 percent in 2025 to 60 percent by 2030 ([Ahmad et al., 2025](#)). Currently on grid capacity of renewable energy stands at 37% which is going to increase as new projects become operational.

The Current Fuel Price Crisis:

Current oil prices fluctuation is impacting Pakistan's import bill. Domestic consumers have to pay additional costs that have an inflationary domino effect on the price of basic goods such as food, utilities and commute. In the case of Pakistan that has been going through a period of economic turmoil would find it hard to absorb these rising energy costs. This will lead to currency depreciation as the rupee weakens against the major currency such as the US dollar. However, Pakistan also witnesses malintent and greed driven motives from its public sector. According to a DAWN News article, Pakistan has enough supply of domestic oil, however, petrol and gas stations are using the commotion caused on the international forum to their advantage, by increasing fuel prices, and refusing to sell to customers at lower rates ([Ali, 2026](#)).

Additionally, this will further put pressure on the country's reserves of foreign exchange. Pakistan's reduced fiscal space due to rising oil prices would limit the government's ability to deliver large fuel subsidies. Due to high public debt and IMF-related reforms the country is forced to reduce subsidies and transfer rising costs to the general public. Likewise the transportation sector is also impacted due to rising costs and reduced profits.

Energy affordability for households will also play a vital role in middle income economies like Pakistan that will see a reduction in its purchasing power parity. Thus, leading to decreased consumption and investment. Moreover, inflation will hamper overall economic growth as prices of goods and services will restrict overall demand. In terms of input costs which will be cutting into profits of businesses that may slow down economic activity. As a result, these rising costs will be transferred on to consumers which may trigger social unrest.

Opportunities for Clean Energy Transition:

Looking closely at the situation this crisis could turn out to be a catalyst to energy transition globally. Last time the Arab-Israel war made a major shift in energy consumption and generation as fuel efficient vehicles were introduced and renewable energy sources were further explored. Pakistan currently stands at a massive crossroads of becoming an energy secure state as it holds the huge potential of generating power from wind and solar energy systems. The ongoing solar rush in the country has shown a rapid transition. More than 2 gigawatts (GW) worth of solar panels have been imported between 2019 and 2025.

It is estimated that Pakistan can meet its present electricity demand by utilizing 0.071% of its land for solar power infrastructure. Also the country holds many wind corridors where wind reaches at the speed of 7.87 per second. These energy solutions could be implemented on roof tops as microgrids by households and businesses. This would make them net energy providers in the coming time. Moreover energy produced from these systems can also be used to charge EVs that would further reduce demand for imported oil fossil fuels.

Challenges to the Energy Transition:

Financial instability and the absence of investors are two of the significant barriers to the country's energy transition. The energy sector in Pakistan, which is burdened by heavy circular debt, unreliable cash flows, and delayed payments to IPPs, hinders the international investors, especially those investing in innovative projects such as wind and solar parks. One example is the government's repeated attempts to attract even a single investor for a 600 MV utility solar park in Muzaffargarh.

Another major structural problem in this sector is caused by circular debt. Circular debt disrupts the financial flow of the whole energy supply chain. Distribution companies are unable to recover the required revenue from consumers, which in turn prevents them from paying the power generation companies. These producers struggle to pay the fuel suppliers and invest in infrastructure upgrades and maintenance, creating a vicious cycle of financial instability ([Ahmad et al., 2025](#)).

Pakistan's circular debt had reached approximately 2.4-2.6 trillion PKR (around USD 9.4 billion). The lack of cash flow and ineffective regulatory frameworks obstruct investment in energy resources especially, in renewables. Heavy reliance on imported fuels drains Pakistan's foreign exchange reserves; subsidies burden the economy, discouraging private sector participation and energy efficiency. The imported fossil fuel, such as LNG and coal, exposes the energy sector to fluctuations in the global energy crisis, similar to one Pakistan is facing nowadays, leading to an increase in energy prices and currency depreciation. All these vulnerabilities collectively impact the transition towards clean energy.

Similarly, inconsistency in policy formulation and implementation represents another barrier to Pakistan's energy transition. Frequent changes of government, changes in priorities, and shifts in energy policies have created an atmosphere of uncertainty for energy developers and investors.

Hence, despite having policies like the “Alternate and Renewable Energy (ARE) policy 2019” centered on bidding for renewable energy projects, the government has been unable to carry out competitive auctions for planned or new renewable projects ([Shahzad & Aruga, 2025](#)). Additionally, some structural incompetencies like complex regulatory procedures, bureaucratic and prolonged approval delays, and transaction issues creates an environment where the development and deployment of renewable energy technology either slow down or completely terminate.

Pakistan's outdated energy infrastructure also hinders the energy transition and integration of renewables or clean energy into the national power system. Renewable energy systems require modern and upgraded transmission infrastructure along with advanced storage capacities and technologies for grid management. Meanwhile, in Pakistan, the grid capacity or the transmission system is very outdated and suffers from technical inefficiency. Pakistan does not have the capacity or revenue to upgrade the energy system on such a larger scale to successfully integrate renewable or clean energy ([Dobermann et al., 2025](#)).

Finally, the political economy of the energy sector of Pakistan acts as another structural barrier to the country's transition to clean energy. Contractual obligations with independent power producers hampers the transition due to fossil fuel-based energy interests of the companies, and the government being indebted to these producer companies further aggravates the situation. Lobbying by fossil fuel industries, governance challenges, corruption, and lack of transparency in energy contracts undermine reforms and efforts made toward the energy transition.

Policy Recommendations:

- An inefficient subsidy structure and issue of pricing have long served as a problem for the Pakistan energy sector. The current energy crisis further burdens the government and the consumers. Experts recommend that the more sustainable approach in such times would involve gradual reforming energy subsidies and shifting toward targeted financial support for vulnerable households rather than universal fuel subsidies. This would allow energy prices to more accurately reflect the actual market cost while allowing the government to cut unnecessary spending.
- The recent rise in fuel prices shows how vulnerable and risky it is for Pakistan to depend on imported fuel. To reduce such risks Pakistan should accelerate its investments in renewables. Since Pakistan has a lot of energy potential, especially in the Sindh and Balochistan region with strong sunlight and ample wind conditions, these regions would make a perfect hub for renewable energy sources. The government can organize auctions and invite foreign and private investors to invest in such projects. Similarly, the government can also provide tax relief and low-interest loans to investors. By investing in modern technologies like smart grids, better transmission lines, and energy storage systems like batteries, Pakistan can transform its outdated grid infrastructure. By upgrading this infrastructure Pakistan can easily integrate new, renewable energy systems.
- The increase in fuel and price will impact transportation costs, industrial costs, and overall inflation in Pakistan. One way to reduce such pressure would be by improving energy-efficiency. This means using less energy to perform the same task. By introducing energy efficient appliances, efficient industrial technologies, installing smart meters, and introducing time-of-use electricity tariffs.
- Finally, keeping in view all of the reforms needed, either structural, governance, or policy reforms, Pakistan cannot achieve its clean and renewable energy targets alone. Building new projects, modernizing and upgrading existing infrastructure, or even installing new infrastructure requires significant capital investment. Cooperation with international finance mechanisms can provide critical financial support, but acquiring such a large sum of capital represents the main hurdle in achieving such targets.

Conclusion:

Pakistan is facing the current fuel crisis as a spillover effect due to the geopolitical tension ongoing in the Middle East. Although not being directly involved in the conflict, Pakistan is facing one of the worst economic crises triggered by this event. Pakistan, being a developing country and already suffering from high inflation and economic instability, could face another devastating impact of this conflict. Rising global oil prices have already translated into higher domestic fuel prices, inflationary pressure, and increased fiscal strain.

However, such a crisis can open critical policy windows for long-term structural and policy changes and an opportunity to adapt to new reforms. The ongoing fuel price surge highlights the risk of high dependence on imported fossil fuel to drive the economy of the state. Policy makers and youth advocates have been raising their voices for the past years on transitioning toward clean energy resources. Transitioning toward clean and renewable energy is not only a strategic imperative but also an environmental necessity.

Ultimately the current fuel crisis should not be viewed as a mere disruption but as a critical turning point for Pakistan's energy policies if analyzed thoroughly, and the crisis can catalyze transition toward a more affordable, secure, environmentally sustainable energy system. This is the time for policymakers and decision makers to seize the opportunity and transform this geopolitical turbulence into a long-term pathway towards energy security and sufficiency, economic reliance, and climate sustainability.

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